

SPATIAL MODELS OF WOOD SPECIES DISTRIBUTION IN FORESTRY SYSTEMS. CASE STUDY – ALPINE AREA OF THE EASTERN CARPATHIANS

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Abstract

The expansion of wood species in meadows and mountain pastures can be considered a phenomenon that manifests itself globally, which has generated, in the last two decades, numerous scientific debates. This process is associated with the decline or even abandonment of traditional agricultural practices specific to mountain areas coupled with the favorable context for the installation of wood species at high altitudes generated by current climate change.

In the present study, with the help of UAV (drone) systems, the mapping, monitoring and determination of the spatial distribution of wood species in the silvopastoral systems in the alpine area of the Eastern Carpathians was performed. The primary data on the spatial distribution of individuals in wood species were obtained by digitizing orthophoto plans generated based on flights performed with a DJI Phantom3 drone equipped with a camera. The study area is located on the southern slope of the Călimani Mountains (Eastern Carpathians), in a secondary succession represented by a compact mass of mountain pine (*Pinus mugo*) and juniper (*Juniperus communis*) with isolated trees of spruce (*Picea abies*).

The analysis of the spatial distribution of spruce trees reveals an aggregate structure at distances greater than 5 m. The application of the models of statistical analysis of the spatial structure (functions F, G, J and L) highlighted the dominance of aggregate structures, the presence of regular structures being found only at small distances (1–5 m), generated mainly by the processes of mutual inhibition of shrubs of juniper and mountain pine, respectively spruce crowns. Knowledge of the spatial and temporal dynamics of changes that occur in the productive and ecological potential of pastoral ecosystems, is a fundamental condition for ensuring sustainable management.

Keywords: *silvopastoral systems, drone, spatial distribution models, spruce.*

INTRODUCTION

The meadows cover about 40% of the total surface of the Earth, which represents approx. 52.5 million km², being absolutely necessary to ensure their sustainable management, in conjunction with the implementation of a long-term monitoring system of their condition and functionality (Capolupo et al., 2015). These ecosystems play an important socio-economic and environmental role through the diversity of services they provide. Thus, they not only provide food and habitat for herbivorous species, but also play a significant role in protecting the environment (conserving water and soil, combating soil erosion, etc.), carbon sequestration and climate regulation (Zhang et al., 2018). However, compared to other ecosystems, grasslands are much more vulnerable to climate change (Parton et al., 1995). Soil surface biomass is the most important indicator of grassland sensitivity to climate change and anthropogenic pressure, requiring qualitative, real-time monitoring of short- and long-term changes (Wang et al., 2017).

The need to monitor mountain pastures and meadows, arises with the structural and functional changes of these ecosystems. In recent decades, there has been a trend of expanding woody vegetation, especially in the mountains. Invasion of trees and shrubs in mountain meadows has been reported in many parts of the world (Wearne and Morgan, 2001; Dullinger et al., 2003). For example, in the United States, an estimated 330 million acres of grassland are subject to shrub invasion, especially in semi-arid western areas (Pacala et al. 2001; Knapp et al. 2008, Eldridge et al., 2011). Australia faces large areas of pastures at high altitudes invaded by trees and/or shrubs (Wearne and Morgan, 2001; Coop and Givnish, 2007). It is also estimated that 13 million hectares of grasslands in South Africa are subject to shrub invasion (Trollope et al., 1989; Eldridge et al., 2011).

More and more studies (Dullinger et al., 2003, Dirnböck and Dullinger, 2004, Peringer and Rosenthal, 2010, Potthoff and Stroth, 2011, Komac et al., 2013, Pornaro et al., 2013, Caviezel et al., 2017, Šenfeldr and Treml, 2020), confirms the existence of the phenomenon of invasion of wood species in meadows and pastures in Europe. This trend of expanding forest and shrubby vegetation in European mountain meadows is an obvious fact especially in the last 5 decades both in the Alps, Pyrenees, but also in the Carpathians (Wiezik et al., 2013).

The main determinant of this successive vegetation dynamics is represented by abandonment (Komac et al., 2013, Pornaro et al., 2013, Šenfeldr and Treml, 2020) or the decline of traditional agricultural practices (harvesting, grazing), a phenomenon observed globally (Gellrich et al., 2007; Gellrich et al., 2008, Koch, 2015). Along with changing land use practices, climate change is also increasingly associated with the phenomenon of wood species invasion of mountain pastures (Weisberg et al., 2007, Eldridge et al., 2011, Komac et al., 2013, Šenfeldr and Treml, 2020, Malfasi and Cannone, 2020).

Pastures and meadows are a significant component of the Carpathian Mountains providing essential ecosystem services (carbon storage, soil erosion prevention, support for the mountain zootechnical system, basic cultural, social, ecological and economic framework for rural mountain communities), but in at the same time, they are sensitive habitats that require close monitoring.

In the current context of climate change, coupled with an increase in anthropogenic pressure on silvopastoral systems, knowledge of the spatial and temporal dynamics of changes in their productive and ecological potential, is a fundamental condition for ensuring sustainable management. Evaluating regional land cover models is the first step towards developing a successful management and conservation plan (Brandt and Townsend, 2006). Monitoring the state of mountain silvopastoral systems in the Carpathians, as well as in the European Union is necessary to achieve the objectives assumed by the Common Agricultural Policy, environmental policies, reducing the effects of climate change, the Habitats Directive, the Nitrates Directive, etc.

The process of monitoring of silvopastoral systems with the help of modern remote sensing techniques is an important component of the national and European strategy in the field of environmental sciences. The development of fine-scale mapping methods of habitat characteristics, based on UAV (drone) images, is a leap forward in the field of ecology, as they allow the capture of details on the structural description of vegetation (Gonçalves et al., 2016). The use of UAV-based systems for land inventory and monitoring is proving to be a great promise, as they can complement or even replace ground measurements (e.g., land cover with shrub species) (Laliberte, et al., 2010).

The incorporation of spatial information in the analysis of biological ecosystems, with special reference to forest or silvopastoral ones, is a central objective in the field of ecology due to the fact that images obtained by remote sensing methods provide new spatial information, easily accessible and workable by current methods. The integration of geostatistical analysis techniques, respectively of methods for quantifying the spatial variability of ecological processes, is a new, integrative step in the complex study of the structure and dynamics of biological ecosystems. Ecological processes have a strong spatial character, the large number of factors involved in the process as well as the level of interaction between them, is a subject of analysis for many research programs.

The objective of this paper is to identify the patterns of spatial distribution of wood species in silvopastoral systems in the Eastern Carpathians, support for understanding the dynamics of wood species expansion in mountain meadows.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study area

In order to highlight the characteristics regarding the dynamics of the woody vegetation in the contact area between the compact forest and the alpine meadow (ecotone), under the report of the spatial structure a research plot was placed on the southern slope of the Călimani Mountains (Eastern Carpathians). The research plot captures a secondary succession of colonization of the alpine meadow, by combining a compact zone of mountain pine and juniper with spruce trees distributed in the mass of subshrubs (Fig. 1). This model of colonization of the alpine meadow by the woody vegetation can be considered a stage, following the situation in which the area was initially invaded by shrubs, later, in the newly created conditions, the spruce start to regenerate. From the increasing of the spruce trees density, a compact spruce forest will be reached at the same time with the gradual disappearance of the shrub species.

Fig. 1. General view of the Călimani research plot

Source: the authors – 2021

The data set

The data collection, in order to evaluate and identify the spatial distribution of the spruce trees was done with the help of a helicopter drone model DJI Phantom 3 Professional. The main features of the drone used are: weight 1280 g, maximum speed 16 m/s, maximum altitude 500 m, maximum flight time – 20–23 minutes, maximum operating distance 3.5–5 km, the model being equipped with a camera with 12.4 Mpx resolution. The operation of the drone was performed in a controlled handling system, through a previous programming of the equipment establishing the flight route, altitude, flight speed, frequency of photographic recordings. Based on this information with known spatial location, through specific processing, high-resolution orthophoto planes were obtained that can be used for measurements and quantitative evaluations.

After the flight, the recorded images were processed with dedicated algorithms for obtaining orthophoto plans and other specific information: the digital surface model, the digital terrain model, the point cloud, using the Pix4D Mapper program.

The orthophoto plan obtained allowed the visual identification of each spruce trees in the research plot. The spatial position of each spruce tree was obtained by manually digitizing them. The geospatial database obtained by manual digitization were checked and corrected for positioning errors. Digitization and verification of geospatial information were performed using the QGIS program.

Modeling the spatial structure

The analysis of the spatial distribution of wood species in the alpine meadows was performed through specific statistical methods to specific spatial processes. In the process of analysis, of identification of a certain spatial model must always take into account the fact that each spatial structure is the result of the action of a certain process or the interactions of several biological processes, at a given point in time and space. The study of the spatial structure, and in this case of the point processes, must be directly correlated with the biological processes that led to this grouping. A punctual spatial model is only an abstraction, because in reality time does not stop being a continuous process. It is important to see the point spatial model as a one-time instance of a complex, continuous process that operates at the spatial level.

A point process is characterized by certain properties such as: total number of events, average and local density, type of structure. The spatial organization of point data defines the type of spatial structure as a zero-dimensional feature of a set of points that describes their location in terms of relative distances from one point to another. Three fundamental types of structure are defined in the literature: randomized structure (random patterns); regular structure; clumped patterns. For the analysis of the spatial structure of the point processes represented by spruce trees, four statistical models based on distance were applied – the F, G, J and Ripley univariate (L) function.

The analysis of the distribution of distances from the nearest neighbor in a point process is performed by cumulative distribution or G function. This is compared with the theoretical model specific to a random Poisson point process, having the form:

$$G(r) = 1 - e^{-\lambda\pi r^2}, \text{ where } r \text{ is the distance.} \quad (1)$$

Values of the experimental G function higher than the theoretical model reflect an aggregate structure, and lower values a regular structure.

Another model of analysis is represented by the function F which allows the analysis of the spaces between the events of a point process. This model is made by analyzing the distances from a point in the field of analysis to the nearest event of the point process. The experimental values are compared with those of a randomized Poisson model with the same intensity. Values of the experimental F function lower than the theoretical model reflect an aggregate structure, and higher values a regular structure. By combining the two distance-based models presented above (F and G) we obtain the function J, defined as follows:

$$J(r) = \frac{1 - G(r)}{1 - F(r)} \quad (2)$$

For a random Poisson type process, the theoretical function J has value 1. For values of J (r) greater than 1 the point process is regular, and for subunit values it is aggregated.

The Ripley statistical model for analyzing the spatial structure of a point process is defined as the number of events expected for a given distance r, having the form:

$$\hat{K}(r) = \frac{a}{n(n-1)} \sum_i \sum_j I(d_{ij} \leq r) e_{ij} \quad (3)$$

For an easier interpretation of the results it is recommended to transform the Ripley K model into a L function, in the form:

$$L(r) = \sqrt{\frac{K(r)}{\pi}} \quad (4)$$

This experimental model is compared with the theoretical one specific to a randomized Poisson type point randomized process. The experimental values higher than the theoretical model reflect an aggregate structure, and the smallest a regular structure. In order to eliminate the margin effect, specific corrections implemented in the IT routines used were applied. Given the high degree of inhomogeneity regarding the density of spruce specimens in the compact mass of shrubs, the use of statistical functions for modeling point spatial processes adapted to inhomogeneous processes is justified.

Statistical analysis was performed in the R statistical programming environment based on the spatstat package (Baddeley et al., 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A stochastic space process can be characterized in terms of its first-order and second-order properties. First-order properties generally describe how the estimated values of the (average) process vary relative to space, and second-order properties describe the covariance (correlation) between process events in different subregions of space. The first-order properties of point spatial processes are described in terms of process intensity, respectively the average number of events per unit area. In order to analyze the interaction between the components of the point process and its variation in space, it is necessary to analyze the

second-order properties or the spatial dependence of a point process. These refer to the relationship between the number of pair events in the studied region.

The Călimani research area represents a possible evolution of the situation in which, following a primary succession on an alpine meadow where shrubby wood species (mountain pine, juniper) have been installed, tree species can be installed (Fig. 2). The evolution of this alpine meadow is typical for many of the mountainous areas of the Eastern Carpathians, being characterized by a significant reduction of anthropogenic pressure through grazing determined in this case by two main factors: significant decrease in the number of grazing animals, especially sheep after 1990, corroborated with the status of protected area established by the establishment of the Călimani National Park. The process of colonization of the meadow with woody species is characterized by the appearance and development of mountain pine and juniper shrubs in a meadow dominated by grassy vegetation represented mainly by tall straws. Subsequently, by increasing the density of the shrubs, a compact mass is formed in which isolated trees of spruce and stone pine regenerated.

Fig. 2. The punctual spatial process of spruce distribution in Călimani

Source: the authors – 2021

The study area is characterized by a compact matrix of juniper and mountain pine shrubs in which isolated trees of spruce are distributed. The research plot has 39.1 ha with a total number of 578 spruce trees. The average density is 14.78 trees per ha, with higher values at the bottom of the study area, located near the compact spruce forest (Fig. 3). There is an obvious gradient of reducing the density of spruce specimens as the altitude and distance from the compact spruce forest, a source of seeds, increase.

Fig. 3. Variation of the density of spruce trees in Călimani

Source: the authors – 2021

Fig. 4. Models of the spatial distribution of spruce trees in Călimani

Source: the authors – 2021

The statistical analysis reveals a clear aggregate structure at distances greater than 10 m, revealing values of the experienced L and G function higher than those related to a randomized point spatial model. The spatial model is of regular type, inhibitory at distances of less than 5–7 m, determined by the processes of competition between spruce trees (Fig. 4). The dynamics of succession in this case is of the type of increasing the density of spruce trees simultaneously with the development of crowns on existing trees. This will lead, over several decades, to the formation of a compact tree, along with the disappearance of shrub species due to lack of light under the canopy of spruce trees. The evolution process is much slower compared to the primary succession, respectively the colonization of the alpine meadow with juniper and mountain pine shrubs.

Woody plants are spreading in many alpine and subalpine ecosystems and a continuous growth of this process is expected in response to land abandonment (Anthelme et al., 2007, Lasanta et al., 2005, Komac et al., 2013) and global warming. (Komac et al., 2013). The decline or even abandonment of traditional agricultural practices, such as grazing, followed by the installation of natural forest is a phenomenon that can be observed globally (Gellrich et al., 2007).

Restrictions on grazing or any anthropogenic activity favor the installation of shrubby or tree species in alpine pastures. Thus, once the pressure exerted by grazing or mowing is eliminated, succession is installed (Tappeiner and Cernusca, 1993). Phenomenon that can be observed in the area analyzed in this study, where with the establishment of a protected natural area through the establishment of the Călimani National Park, restrictions on pastoral activities were imposed. These policies favored the succession of vegetation from grassland dominated by grassy species to shrubby species (juniper, mountain pine) and further to the emergence and development of spruce trees.

Invasion of tree and shrub species in pastures is a notable change in land cover, respectively a matter of concern for the sustainable management of mountain biodiversity (Bayle et al., 2019). This requires special attention in terms of monitoring, assessment and mapping of these ecosystems. Current technologies represented by the accessibility of drone use open new research opportunities (Laliberte et al., 2010). These technologies are preferred due to their small size, high maneuverability, load-to-weight ratio, low costs (Tomczak et al., 2012). UAVs can also have a higher payload, in addition to cameras (including video cameras), some can carry multispectral radiometers, thermal radiometers and even hyperspectral devices (Rango et al., 2006).

The information obtained with the help of these systems helps us to understand the processes that determine the change of land use. Understanding these processes is important in mountain areas because they are related to a variety of environmental consequences (Gellrich et al., 2007) with a significant impact on the structure and functions of the ecosystem. Knowledge of the issue of alpine meadows and pastures is a real support for decision makers and for the implementation of sustainable management in these areas.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of UAV systems freely or programmed allows to obtain relevant spatial information on the state and dynamics of silvopastoral systems, especially in the transition zone between the forest and the mountain and alpine meadow. These areas are characterized by steep slopes, high level differences and often covered with dense woody vegetation.

Following the research carried out in the Călimani Mountains, different models of spatial organization of wood species within the silvopastoral systems were analyzed, characterized by a specific succession dynamic, respectively of recolonization of the mountain meadow with shrub wood species, followed by a secondary succession of spruce in compact mass of shrubs.

The application of the models of statistical analysis of the spatial structure (functions F, G, J and L) highlighted the dominance of the aggregate structure, in the analyzed area, the presence of regular structures being found only at small distances (1–5 m), generated mainly by mutual inhibition of juniper and mountain pine, respectively spruce crowns.

Monitoring the dynamics of the succession process in this area in the coming decades, with the same methodology for obtaining primary data (drones) and statistical analysis (point processes) will determine the speed of development and expansion of woody vegetation, offering the prospect of developing dynamic models temporal, adapted to the specifics of the mountainous area of the Eastern Carpathians.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Anthelme, F., Jean-Charles, V., Brun, J.-J.**, (2007), *Shrub encroachment in the Alps gives rise to the convergence of sub-alpine communities on a regional scale*. Journal of Vegetation Science 18, 355e362.
- Baddeley, A., Rubak, E., Turner, R.**, (2015), *Spatial point patterns: methodology and applications with R*. CRC Press.
- Bayle A., Carlson B. Z., Thierion V., Isenmann M. and Choler P.**, (2019), *Improved Mapping of Mountain Shrublands Using the Sentinel-2 Red-Edge Band*, Remote Sens, 11, 2807; doi:10.3390/rs11232807
- Brandt J. S., and Townsend P.A.** (2006), *Land use–land cover conversion, regeneration and degradation in the high elevation Bolivian Andes*. Landsc Ecol 2006:21:607–23.
- Capolupo, A., Kooistra, L., Berendonk, C., Boccia, L., Suomalainen, J.**, (2015), *Estimating Plant Traits of Grasslands from UAV-Acquired Hyperspectral Images: A Comparison of Statistical Approaches*. ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf. 2015, 4, 2792–2820; DOI:10.3390/ijgi4042792.
- Caviezal C., Hunziker M., Kuhn N.J.**, (2011), *Impacts of shrub encroachment on ecosystem structure and functioning: towards a global synthesis*, Ecology Letters, 14: 709–722.
- Coop J.D., and Givnish T.J.**, (2007), *Spatial and temporal patterns of recent forest encroachment in montane grasslands of the Valles Caldera, New Mexico, USA*, Journal of Biogeography (J. Biogeogr.):34, 914–927.
- Dirnböck T. and Dullinger S.**, (2004), *Habitat distribution models, spatial autocorrelation, functional traits and dispersal capacity of alpine plant species*, Journal of Vegetation Science 15: 77–84.
- Dullinger S., Dirnböck T. and Grabherr G.**, (2003), *Patterns of Shrub Invasion into High Mountain Grasslands of the Northern Calcareous Alps, Austria*, Arctic, Antarctic, and Alpine Research, Vol. 35, No. 4, pp. 434–441. [https://doi.org/10.1657/1523-0430\(2003\)035\[0434:POSIIH\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1657/1523-0430(2003)035[0434:POSIIH]2.0.CO;2)
- Eldridge D.E., Bowker M.A., Maestre F.T., Roger E., Reynolds J.F. and Whitford W.G.**, (2011), *Impacts of shrub encroachment on ecosystem structure and functioning: towards a global synthesis*, Ecology Letters, (2011) 14: 709–722, doi: 10.1111/j.1461-0248.2011.01630.x
- Gellrich M., Baur P., Koch B., Zimmermann N.E.**, (2007), *Agricultural land abandonment and natural forest re-growth in the Swiss mountains: A spatially explicit economic analysis*, Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment 118:93–108.

- Gellrich M., Baur P., Robinson B.H., Bebi P.,** (2008), *Combining classification tree analyses with interviews to study why sub-alpine grasslands sometimes revert to forest: A case study from the Swiss Alps*, *Agricultural Systems* 96: 124–138.
- Gonçalves J., Henriques R., Alves P., Sousa-Silva R., Monteiro A.T., Lomba A., Bruno Marcos B., Honrado J.,** (2016), *Evaluating an unmanned aerial vehicle-based approach for assessing habitat extent and condition in fine-scale early successional mountain mosaics*, *Applied Vegetation Science* 19: 132–146.
- Knapp, A.K., Briggs, J.M., Collins, S.L., Archer, S.R., Bret-Harte, M.S., Ewers, B.E. et al.** (2008). *Shrub encroachment in North American grasslands: shifts in growth form dominance rapidly alters control of ecosystem carbon inputs*. *Glob. Change Biol.*, 14, 615–623.
- Koch B., Edwards P.J., Blanckenhorn W. U., Walter T., Hofer G.,** (2015), *Shrub Encroachment Affects the Diversity of Plants, Butterflies, and Grasshoppers on Two Swiss Subalpine Pastures*, *Arctic, Antarctic, and Alpine Research*, 47:2, 345–357, DOI: 10.1657/AAAR0013-093
- Komac B., Kefi S., Nuche P., Escós J., Alados C.L.,** (2013), *Modeling shrub encroachment in subalpine grasslands under different environmental and management scenarios*, *Journal of Environmental Management* 121: 160–169.
- Laliberte A.S., Herrick J.E., Rango A., and Winters C.,** (2010), *Acquisition, Orthorectification, and Object-based Classification of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Imagery for Rangeland Monitoring*, *Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing* Vol. 76, No. 6, pp. 661–672.
- Lasanta, T., Vicente-Serrano, S., Cuadrat-Prats, J.M.,** (2005), *Mountain Mediterranean landscape evolution caused by the abandonment of traditional primary activities: a study of the Spanish Central Pyrenees*. *Applied Geography* 25, 47–65.
- Malfasi F. and Cannone N.,** (2020), *Climate Warming Persistence Triggered Tree Ingression After Shrub Encroachment in a High Alpine Tundra*, *Ecosystems* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-020-00495-7>
- Pacala, S.W., Hurtt, G.C., Baker, D., Peylin, P., Houghton, R.A., Birdsey, R.A. et al.** (2001), *Consistent land- and atmosphere-based US carbon sink estimates*. *Science*, 292, 2316–2320.
- Parton, W.J.; Scurlock, J.M.O.; Ojima, D.S.; Schimel, D.S.; Hall, D.O.; Members, S.G.,** (1995), *Impact of climate change on grassland production and soil carbon worldwide*. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 1995, 1, 13–22; <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.1995.tb00002.x>.
- Peringer A. and Rosenthal G.,** (2011), *Establishment patterns in a secondary tree line ecotone*, *Ecological Modelling* 222:3120– 3131.
- Pornaro C., Schneider M. C., Stefano Macolino S.,** (2013), *Plant species loss due to forest succession in Alpine pastures depends on site conditions and observation scale*, *Biological Conservation* 161:213–222.
- Potthoff, K. and Stroth, V.,** (2011), *Patterns of vegetation change on alpine mountain summer farms in Norway*. *Geografiska Annaler: Series A, Physical Geography*, 93, 163–174. DOI:10.1111/j.1468-0459.2011.00427.x.
- Rango A., Laliberte A., Steele C., Herrick J.E., Bestelmeyer B., Schmutge T., Roanhorse A., Jenkins V.,** (2006), *Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles for Rangelands: Current Applications and Future Potentials*, *Environmental Practice* 8 (3): 159–168, DOI: 10.1017/S1466046606060224
- Šenfeldr M. and Václav Tremil V.,** (2020), *Which generative reproduction characteristics determine successful establishment of the subalpine shrub *Pinus mugo*?* *Journal of Vegetation Science*: 31:403–415.
- Tappeiner U. and Cernusca A.,** (1993), *Alpine meadows and pastures after abandonment*, *Pirineos*, 141–142: 97 a 118, JACA. <http://pirineos.revistas.csic.es>
- Tomczak, R.J., Janina Rudowicz-Nawrocka J., Kujawa S., Mueller W.,** (2012), *Autonomous flying system for grasslands and fields monitoring*. Fourth International Conference on Digital Image Processing (ICDIP 2012), DOI: 10.1117/12.946047.

- Trollope, W.S.W., Hobson, F.O., Danckwerts, J.E. & Van Niekerk, J.P.** (1989), *Encroachment and control of undesirable plants*. In: Veld management in the Eastern Cape (eds. Danckwerts, J.E. & Van Niekerk, J.P.). Department of Agriculture and Water Supply, Pretoria, South Africa, pp. 73–89.
- Wang, D., Xin, X., Shao, Q., Brolly, M., Zhu, Z., Chen, J.**, (2017), *Modeling Aboveground Biomass in Hulunber Grassland Ecosystem by Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Discrete Lidar*. *Sensors*, 17, 180; DOI:10.3390/s17010180.
- Wearne, L. J., and Morgan, J. W.**, (2001), *Recent forest encroachment into subalpine grasslands near Mount Hotham, Victoria, Australia*. *Arctic, Antarctic, and Alpine Research*, 33: 369–377.
- Weisberg, P.J., Lingua E., and Pillai R. B.**, (2007), *Spatial Patterns of Pinyon–Juniper Woodland Expansion in Central Nevada*, *Rangeland Ecol Manage* 60:115–124.
- Wiezik, M., Svitok, M., Wieziková, A., Dovčiak, M.**, (2013), *Shrub encroachment alters composition and diversity of ant communities in abandoned grasslands of western Carpathians*. *Biodivers. Conserv.* 22, 2305–2320.
- Zhang H., Sun Y., Chang L., Qin Y., Chen J., QinY., Du J., Yi S., and Wang Y.**, (2018), *Estimation of Grassland Canopy Height and Aboveground Biomass at the Quadrat Scale Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle*, *Remote Sens.* 2018, 10, 851; doi:10.3390/rs10060851.